

Readme file for Data from “Comparison between the kinematics for kangaroo rat hopping on a solid versus sand surface”

Kinematic data set

Digitized x,y data from hopping on solid surface are named: “tDD**Sol3_ *_ *XYpts.csv” where the * indicates identifiers related to animal number or video number.

The starts of the hops are saved in “starts.xls” and ends of the hops are saved in “toeoffs.xls”

The Matlab script to analyze the kinematic data and obtain joint angles and speeds is in the software “jumpAnglesJoseph_5_11_18.m”

Digitized x,y data from hopping on solid surface are named: “tDD**San3_ *_ *XYpts.csv” where the * indicates identifiers related to animal number or video number.

The starts of the hops are saved in “starts_sand.xls” and ends of the hops are saved in “toeoffs_sand.xls”.

The Matlab script to analyze the kinematic data and obtain joint angles and speeds is in the software “jumpAnglesJoseph_5_11_18_sand.m”

Note that the “_sand” of the filenames was added so files with the same name were not uploaded. The “_sand” would have to be removed on the starts and toeoffs files and the Matlab script.

“testing.m” has a Matlab script with the Wilcoxon sign test.

“Data_Analysis_3_16_18.xlsx” is an excel file with summary data.

“sand_9_3_21.mat” is a Matlab file with summary kinematic data for the sand hopping

“solid_9_3_21.mat” is a Matlab file with summary kinematic data for the solid hopping

“kinematicMeanStd.m” and “midstanceELtest.m” are Matlab scripts for statistical tests of the kinematic data.

Sand Penetration Tests

Raw data are in the files: “Sand##*_ \$.ddf” which are in the format that the data collection software uses. The ## indicates the depth of sand (e.g., 15 is 1.5 cm), the * is an experiment identifier, and \$ is the trial number.

“PlotMultipleTrials.m” is a Matlab script that reads the files and estimates the penetration resistance (called “stiffnesses”) and plots the data.

“stiffnessData.mat” is the Matlab data of the penetration resistances for each depth

“PostHocSand.m” is a Matlab script that reads stiffnessData.mat and runs the ANOVA and post hoc tests.